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FIDELIS, European Network of Trustworthy Digital Repositories Follow-up Position Statement on the EOSC Federation June 2026

This document is a follow-up to the FIDELIS TDR Network's (hereafter referred to as the Network) [Position Statement of October 2025](#) on the EOSC Federation Handbook. It reaffirms the Network's core message and reports on steps taken since then. The Network calls for the establishment of a structured dialogue between the EOSC Association and Trustworthy Digital Repositories (TDRs).

The ambition of the European Open Science Cloud (EOSC) is to develop a 'Web of FAIR Data and Services' for science in Europe. Realising this ambition depends on data - and data lives in repositories. Not just any repositories, but TDRs: organisations that ensure data is findable, accessible, interoperable, and reusable not only at the moment of deposit, but in the long-term. The EOSC Federation needs data, and TDRs hold that data.

For this reason, the Network emphasised in its October 2025 Position Statement that the requirements for repositories to participate in and offer their data through the EOSC Federation must be clear and feasible. Requirements that are ambiguous or disproportionate risk excluding the very organisations that the EOSC Federation depends on. The Network called for a structured dialogue with the EOSC Association to ensure that TDRs can meaningfully engage with and contribute to the Federation.

What the FIDELIS Network has done since October 2025

The Network has acted on this commitment. FIDELIS engaged with the Scientific Repository Working Group of the EOSC Federation Build-up Group, contributing expertise, survey data and practical perspectives. The FIDELIS project provided detailed feedback to the EOSC Federation Handbook and presented at the EOSC Symposium in November 2025, making the case for why TDRs are indispensable for data sovereignty — a theme of growing importance as the European research infrastructure seeks strategic autonomy over its data assets. The engagement of TDRs in the EOSC Federation has been a regular item of discussion in FIDELIS TDR Network meetings.

The Scientific Repository Working Group of the EOSC Federation Build-up Group has since concluded its work and the EOSC Association's [FAIR Metrics and Digital Objects Task Force](#) will lead an activity to define a common set of FAIR recommendations for repositories. While this will be an important step forward, more clarity is needed on how the TDR community can engage to contribute to effective requirements and onboarding processes for TDRs in the EOSC Federation.

A renewed call for dialogue

The FIDELIS TDR Network renews its call for structured engagement: a dedicated liaison role between the EOSC Association and the community of TDRs, in particular on the topic of TDRs in the EOSC Federation. The Network's membership — now comprising over 70 European repositories —

represents a wealth of practical cross-disciplinary knowledge about what repositories can and cannot deliver, under what conditions and on what timeline. Harnessing this knowledge is not only in the interest of repositories: it is essential for EOSC to build a Federation that is grounded in operational reality and capable of delivering on its promise of a web of FAIR data.

The FIDELIS TDR Network stands ready to contribute.